

Data Management Plan Template

Via this template you can create your data management plan (DMP).

This DMP is for **your entire research project**, not only for the part that involves human participants or ERB approval. Please think about all data you will create or use, such as:

- data from **experiments, simulations, models, logs, sensors, benchmarks, software/code**, etc., and
- data from **human participants** (if any), such as surveys, interviews, observations, or usage data.

We understand that at the start of a research project many details are still uncertain. You are not expected to know everything yet. Instead:

- be **as specific as you can now** about the data you are likely to handle over the whole project
- if something is **not yet decided**, describe the **main options** you are considering
- remember that this DMP is a **living document**: you are expected to **update it** whenever your project design, data, or procedures change.

Questions: If you have questions please add them at the end of the form as a comment under "Activity"

Save: Click "Save" at the bottom of the form to save the information you provided

Update: Click "Update DMP" on the right-hand panel of the request.

For the most common questions please have a look at the [FAQs page](#).

This template has been approved by NWO, ZonMw, and the European Research Council.

General Project Information

1. Project Title / Study name*

2. Are you a?*

Bachelor student

Master student

Researcher (PhD, academic staff)

Other

2a. Please clarify the "other" option*

3. Primary Contact Name (Student or Researcher)*

4. Primary Contact Email (Student or Researcher)*

5. Supervisor(s) Name(s)

6. Supervisor(s) email address(es)

7. Department*

Select...

7a. Please write your affiliation *

8. What is the purpose of this study? (select all that apply)*

Educational purposes (as part of a course)

Scientific purposes (possibly leading to a publication)

8a. For what course is this required?*

9. Start date of data collection*

10. End date of data collection*

11. Estimated end date of the project *

12. Please add the name and institution of your collaborators below (optional):

13. Does your project receive external funding (e.g., NWO, relevant for special regulations from funders)?*

Yes

No

13a. Is your funder?*

Dutch Research Council (NWO)

European Commission (EC)

ZonMw

Other...

13b. Please provide the name of your funder*

13c. Please provide your grant number(s).*

14. What are your main research questions?*

14b. What data will be collected or produced, and what existing data will be re-used? (Select all that apply)*

Interviews or survey questionnaire

Audio and video recordings

Electronic lab notes (text or OneNote)

Imaging or video collected by brain-imaging or other techniques

Measurement data (e.g., experiments, sensors, heart rate)

Location data (e.g., from app used by the participant)

Social media content

Registry data (e.g., CBS, BioBank, etc.)

Device designs, protocols developed, tested and used during the experiments

Analysis codes, algorithms, simulation modelling data

Other

14c. Please specify*

15. Are there humans directly or indirectly participating in your study?*

Yes

No

15a. Where will the data come from? (Select all that apply)*

- New data collected by me or my research team
- New data collected together with external (outside TU/e) collaborators
- My own previously collected data
- Corporate data from TU/e (student and/or staff data)
- Data obtained from another party
- Data from a public data repository/publicly available data
- Other...

15b. Please specify*

15c. Please add the link to the data.

15b. Has the previously collected data been approved by an ERB (either internal or external)

- Yes
- No

15c. Please check the box that indicates the relevant study population *

- Students
- General healthy population
- General population with specific feature, e.g., pregnancy, specifically (write the feature in the box "other")
- Patients, specifically (write the feature in the box "other")
- Other

15d. Please specify*

15e. Age category of participants*

- Younger than 12 years of age
- 12 to 15 years old
- 16 to 17 years old
- 18 years or older

16. Do you collect/process personal data (including data required for both recruitment and to answer your research question)?*

- Yes
- No
- Both personal and non-personal data

17. Please select which of the following (special category) personal data do you collect/process?*

Select...

17a. Please specify what data will you collect/process.*

18. Is the data going to be anonymized or pseudonymized?*

- Pseudonymize
- Anonymize
- No

19. Please describe how will the data be pseudonymized/anonymized*

19a. Which tool will you use to pseudonymize/anonymize the data?

20. Is it anonymized personal data?*

Yes

No

20a. Please explain how was the personal data anonymized and it is considered anonymous for TU/e?*

20b. Please describe the type of data?*

20c. What is the non-personal data you collect?*

21. Where will the data come from? (Select all that apply)*

Fully theoretical research project

New data collected only by me or my research team

New data collected together with external (outside TU/e) collaborators

My own previously collected data

Corporate data from TU/e (e.g. living labs data)

Data obtained from another party

Data from a public data repository/publicly available data

Other...

22. Please describe the type of data*

22b. Please add the link to the data.

23. Do you share and/or receive personal or IP-protected data from third parties as part of this study?*

No

Yes, I share and/or receive data from external parties that are located in the EU/EEA

Yes, I share and/or receive data from external parties that are located outside the EU/EEA

23a. Will you process personal data in China, Russia, Iran, or North Korea?*

Yes

No

23b. Please provide the name of the institution/company/organization and the country where they are located. Please add all the parties involved (if there are several). *

24. Does the project already have any agreements with the external party (e.g. Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA), data sharing agreement, consortium agreement, etc.)?*

Yes

No

24a. Please attach the agreement here*

Research Data Management Information

During Research

25. Which of the following tools will you use to process the data (including project documentation)? (Select all that apply, if they are not in the list click on "Other" and add them below, you can add several ones in the same box)*

Data Foundry

Limesurvey

Manual transcription

Matlab

Microsoft Excel

Microsoft Forms

Microsoft Teams

Microsoft Word

Overleaf

Python

Qualtrics

R

SPSS

Voice/video recording using phone in flight mode

Other...

25a. Please provide the name of the tool(s):*

26. Where will the data (including project documentation) be stored *during* the study? (Select all that apply)*

Select...

26a. Please specify:*

27. How much data (including project documentation) will you approximately collect or reuse?*

<10 GBs

10's of GBs

100's of GBs

<10 TBs

10's TBs

27a. Do you need any special processing/tools for your data?*

Trusted Research Environment for highly confidential data (myDRE)

Data encryptor (Cryptomator Hub)

High Performance Computer (HPC)

No

Other...

I need advice

After Research

28. Will you store (meta)data for future research? (Select all that apply)*

- Yes, by publishing the (meta)data in a trusted repository openly
- Yes, by publishing the (meta)data in a trusted repository under restricted access
- Yes, by publishing articles (fully theoretical research project)
- Yes, by retaining in a storage solution
- No
- I need advice

28a. In which repository will you publish your data?*

- 4TU.ResearchData
- Figshare
- OSF
- Zenodo
- Other...
- I need advice

28b. Please add the name of the repository*

28c. Do you already have one or multiple DOIs? Please add them here.

28d. In which storage solution will you retain the data?*

Select...

28e. In which storage solution will you retain the data?*

28f. Please elaborate on the reasons why you cannot store the data for future research? *

29. What documentation and/or software code will be deposited with the data?*

- README file
- metadata file
- Codebook
- Logbook
- Analysis script
- Other...

29a. Please specify what other data documentation files will be deposited with the data

30. What (license) conditions will apply to the data you will publish? (Select all that apply)*

- CC-BY 4.0 (free reuse with credits, most used license)
- CC0 (free reuse without credits)
- MIT license (software, code, scripts)
- Other (specify which terms and conditions apply to reuse)
- I need advice

30a. Please specify the license:*

31. QUESTION FROM FUNDER: Indicate which metadata standard will be provided to help others identify and discover the data. (Select all that apply)*

- DataCite (used by 4TU.ResearchData and Zenodo)
- Dublin Core (used by Figshare and Dryad)

DCAT (Health RI)

DDI (MRI scans, health data)

Other...

I need advice

31a. Please provide the name of the metadata standard you will use. *

32. QUESTION FROM FUNDER: When will the data be available for re-use? *

As soon as article is published

Upon completion of the project

After completion of project (with restricted access)

Other...

32a. Please elaborate: *

33. How long will data (including project documentation) be stored after the end of the project? *

10 years at the TU/e archive (Following the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity)

10 years at another archive (Following the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity)

Other...

33a. Please provide the name of the archive*

33b. Please provide the link to the archive*

34. QUESTION FROM FUNDER: What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)? *

Privacy Checklist Information

35. Will your project involve the processing of personal data on a large scale? *

Yes, I will be collecting data from more than 10.000 data subjects

Yes, I will be collecting data from more than 1.000 data subjects all belonging to the same geographical region (province)

No

35a. Please indicate an approximated number of participants, and the location of where the data will be coming from?*

36. Does this processing activity involve the use of new or innovative technologies? *

Yes

No

36a. Please explain what new technology and how will it be used?*

37. Does your study involve systematic (c.q. automated) monitoring of persons? *

Yes

No

37a. Please explain how?*

38. Will the study include data processing activities that prevent data subjects from exercising their rights or using a service or contract?*

Yes

no

38a. Please explain how?*

39. Will the study process personal data to score, rank or profile persons?*

Yes

no

39a. Please explain which personal data will be used and how it will be used?*

40. Does your data processing include activities that involves composing "blacklists", covert or secret investigations, fraud prevention, credit scores, camera surveillance data, employee monitoring, large scale processing of location/GPS data and/or internet-of-things data?*

Yes

no

40a. Please explain which processing activity and why?*

41. Will the processing activity involve automated decision-making with legal effect or similar substantial effect? *

Yes

No

41a. Please explain how?*

42. Are or will datasets be linked or combined to perform this processing activity?*

Yes

No

42a. Please explain where the data will be coming from and how it will combined?*

43. In case you answer "Yes" to any of the questions from the Privacy Checklist and you already have an approved Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) for this project, please attach it here:

44. I want my DMP to be manually revised by my data steward? *

Yes

No

45. Approval from your supervisor

By checking this box, I confirm that this DMP has been discussed and approved by my supervisor(s).

Please wait a minute or so and **refresh** the page manually to see the next steps.